

Plate Map: 3D Seeding												
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
A	No Cells											
B	No Cells	Cells	Cells	Cells	Cells	Cells	Cells	Cells	Cells	Cells	Cells	No Cells
C	No Cells	Cells	Cells	Cells	Cells	Cells	Cells	Cells	Cells	Cells	Cells	No Cells
D	No Cells	Cells	Cells	Cells	Cells	Cells	Cells	Cells	Cells	Cells	Cells	No Cells
E	No Cells	Cells	Cells	Cells	Cells	Cells	Cells	Cells	Cells	Cells	Cells	No Cells
F	No Cells	Cells	Cells	Cells	Cells	Cells	Cells	Cells	Cells	Cells	Cells	No Cells
G	No Cells	Cells	Cells	Cells	Cells	Cells	Cells	Cells	Cells	Cells	Cells	No Cells
H	No Cells											
Matrigel	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+

Plate Map: 3D Treatments Days 2-8													
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	DMSO
A	No Cells	-											
B	No Cells	Tx-2	No Cells	-									
C	No Cells	Tx-2	No Cells	-									
D	No Cells	Tx-1	Tx-1	Tx-2	No Cells	-							
E	No Cells	Tx-1	Tx-1	Tx-2	No Cells	-							
F	No Cells	Tx-2	No Cells	-									
G	No Cells	Tx-2	No Cells	-									
H	No Cells	-											

Plate Map: 3D Treatments Days 8-14													
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	DMSO
A	No Cells	-											
B	No Cells	99.5	27.6	7.71	2.24	0.498	0.249	0.0461	0.0128	0.00361	0.000995	No Cells	+
C	No Cells	99.5	27.6	7.71	2.24	0.498	0.249	0.0461	0.0128	0.00361	0.000995	No Cells	+
D	No Cells	Tx-1	Tx-1	Tx-2	Tx-2	Tx-2	Tx-2	Tx-2	Tx-2	Tx-3	Tx-3	No Cells	-
E	No Cells	Tx-1	Tx-1	Tx-2	Tx-2	Tx-2	Tx-2	Tx-2	Tx-2	Tx-3	Tx-3	No Cells	+
F	No Cells	99.5	27.6	7.71	2.24	0.498	0.249	0.0461	0.0128	0.00361	0.000995	No Cells	+
G	No Cells	99.5	27.6	7.71	2.24	0.498	0.249	0.0461	0.0128	0.00361	0.000995	No Cells	+
H	No Cells	-											

Group	TSH (1 mIU/ml)	Treatment	Concentration	Units	Technical Replicates	MIE_Target	Classification
Tx - 1	No	Negative	NA	NA	2	NA	Control_Baseline
Tx - 2	Yes	Vehicle	0.5	%	6	TSHR	Control_Solvent
Tx - 3	Yes	K1 - 70	1	µg/ml	2	TSHR	Control_Antagonist
Cmpd 1	Yes	Methomyl	0.001 -100	µM	1	NA	Reference_Negative
Cmpd 2	Yes	Methimazole	0.001 -100	µM	1	TPO	Reference_Antagonist
Cmpd 3	Yes	6-Propyl-2-thiouracil	0.001 -100	µM	1	TPO	Reference_Antagonist
Cmpd 4	Yes	Sodium perchlorate	0.001 -100	µM	1	NIS	Reference_Antagonist